

Non-Linear Characteristics of Thin, Large Planform, Orthotropic Plates with Initial Imperfections

I. H. Marshall

Department of Mech. & Prod. Engineering, Paisley College of Technology, High Street, Paisley, Renfrewshire PA1 2BE, Scotland

ABSTRACT

A theoretical analysis of the non-linear characteristics of laterally loaded, thin, rectangular, orthotropic plates with initial imperfections is presented herein. In particular the behaviour of large planform plates is considered and general design guidelines established. Symmetrical and unsymmetrical modes of initial deformation are investigated.

INTRODUCTION

The load/deflection characteristics of thin, laterally loaded rectangular plates has been the subject of numerous past papers and is well understood. This is equally true of plates with isotropic, orthotropic and to some extent anisotropic material properties. Typical examples of previous work in this field is given in references (1) to (5) inclusive. The effects of initial imperfections or "deviations from flatness" on such structural elements has also been considered in some detail in previous investigations. Generally speaking, however, these investigations have confined their attentions to the case of in-plane compression with imperfection magnitudes of one tenth of the plate thickness receiving most attention. A wide variety of edge boundary conditions have also been considered.

One area which appears to have received little attention in the past is the case of orthotropic platework elements with initial imperfections subjected to lateral loading on the convex face. Under these loading conditions such plates can undergo dynamic changes of shape i.e. snap-buckle. The possibility of snap-buckling depends on a number of parameters e.g. magnitude and form of initial imperfection, plate thickness, material properties, etc. The present investigation considers in detail the stability characteristics of large planform orthotropic plates subjected to uniform lateral pressure with symmetrical and unsymmetrical modes of initial deformation. Simply supported plate edges are considered and imperfection magnitudes of up to ten times the plate thickness investigated. The influence of unsymmetrical or bifurcation buckling on the load carrying capability of such plates is also clarified. The present investigation forms a natural extension to previously published work on laterally loaded orthotropic plates with initial curvature (6) (7) (8) and initial imper-

fections (9) (10). At this stage it may be beneficial to briefly review the phenomenon of snap-buckling.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SNAP-BUCKLING EFFECT

The type of load-deflection relationship typical of curved plates, laterally loaded on the convex face, is shown in Fig.1. In this figure it is assumed that the plate will deform symmetrically. The extent of the non-linearity of the above relationship depends on a number of factors, viz. type of lateral loading, edge boundary conditions, plate initial curvature, plate thickness, material properties, etc.

On incremental application of the load, the load-deflection curve equilibrium path will follow the stable portion of the curve from O to B. At point B (the critical point), any increase in load will cause the panel to snap-buckle to point D. If the load is further increased, the panel stiffness will increase as indicated.

On reduction of the load, the curve will again pass through point D but this time it will continue to point C. Further reduction of the load will cause a second snap from point C to point A.

Thus for any value of load in region $P_A > P > P_B$ there will be three possible values of equilibrium displacement. It should be noted that if unsymmetrical behaviour occurs during the snapping process it will have the effect of causing bifurcation at (say) point E.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Governing Equations

The von Karman-type large deflection compatibility equation for the case of an orthotropic plate with initial imperfections can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + \alpha \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} = E_y \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 \omega_0}{\partial x \partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega_0}{\partial w^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega_0}{\partial y^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

An equation similar to equation (1) can be formed from equilibrium considerations. However, as an alternative to solving the equilibrium equation, the total energy of the system will be minimised according to the Ritz technique. The total energy of the system comprises the energy of mid-plane straining U_s , the bending energy U_B and the load potential energy U_p .

Thus:

$$U_T = U_S + U_B + U_p \quad (2)$$

where

$$U_S = \frac{h}{2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \left[\frac{1}{E_x} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 - 2 \frac{\nu_x}{E_x} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{1}{G} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \right] dx dy \quad (3)$$

$$U_B = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \left[D_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 2D_3 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + D_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 \right] dx dy \quad (4)$$

$$U_P = - \int_d^e \int_f^g \omega \cdot q_z dx dy \quad (5)$$

where d, e, f and g are the limits of integration and q_z is the transverse load on the plate per unit area.

The plate lateral deflection and membrane stresses can be stated as general Fourier series of the form:

$$\omega(x,y) = \sum_m \sum_n \omega_{mn} m(x)n(y) \quad (6)$$

$$F(x,y) = \sum_j \sum_k F_{jk} j(x)k(y) \quad (7)$$

The plate edge boundary conditions will be considered as those consistent with 'simple supports'. With reference to Fig.2 these can be written as:

$$\text{along } x = 0, a \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{along } y = 0, b$$

Flexural bcs

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= 0 & \omega &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} &= 0 & \nu_x \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Membrane bcs

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} &= 0 & \frac{\partial^2 F}{x^2} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} &= 0 & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

It will be noted that the boundary conditions of stress-free plate edges as stated in equation (9) will allow tangential edge displacements to occur.

Equation (8) can be satisfied by stating equation (6) in the form:

$$\omega = \sum_m \sum_n \omega_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \quad m, n = 1, 2, 3 \quad (10)$$

Also, equation (9) can be satisfied by stating equation (7) as:

$$F = F_{jk} \sum_j \sum_k \left[\cos \frac{j\pi x}{a} - 1 \right] \left[\cos \frac{k\pi y}{b} - 1 \right] \quad (11)$$

The plate initial deflections can be similarly considered as Fourier series of the type:

$$\omega_0 = \sum_p \sum_q \omega_{pq} \sin \frac{p\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{q\pi y}{b} \quad p, q = 1, 2, 3 \quad (12)$$

It will be noted that equation (12) allow symmetrical and unsymmetrical forms of initial plate deflections to be considered.

In previous work (6) it has been shown that the use of relatively few terms in the aforementioned Fourier series yields acceptable accuracy in the final analysis. Thus, since the present analysis is not really concerned with loads appreciably greater than the snap-buckling or critical load the following series will be deemed suitable.

$$\omega = \sum_{m=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^1 \omega_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \quad (13)$$

$$\omega_o = \sum_{p=1}^2 \sum_{q=1}^1 \omega_{opq} \sin \frac{p\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{q\pi y}{b} \quad (14)$$

$$F = \sum_{j=0}^1 \sum_{k=0}^1 F_{jk} \cos \frac{j\pi x}{a} - 1 \quad \cos \frac{k\pi y}{b} - 1 \quad (15)$$

For this case, the boundary equations (8) and (9) cannot be satisfied by any finite solution of equation (1). Hence a solution to the compatibility equation (1) will be sought using the Galerkin integration technique. A full explanation of this method is contained in reference(11)

The Galerkin method requires satisfaction of the following series of equations.

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b \left[\frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + \alpha \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} \right] \imath_1(x)t(y) dx dy$$

$$= \int_0^a \int_0^b \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \omega_o}{\partial x \partial y} \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega_o}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega_o}{\partial y^2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} \right] \imath_1(x)t(y) dx dy \quad (16)$$

where $\imath_1(x)t(y)$ is the differential of the stress function with respect to each chosen coefficient in turn. Solution of equation (16) yields a relationship between stress function coefficients F_{jk} and deflection function coefficients ω_{mn} and ω_{opq} . Thus, by substituting equation (13), (14) and (15) into energy equations (3), (4) and (5) and noting the results of equation (16) the total energy of the system can be written in terms of deflection function coefficients only.

Minimising the resulting expression for the total energy (U_T) of the system with respect to each of the chosen deflection function coefficients yields a set of simultaneous non-linear algebraic equations equal in number to the chosen number of terms in the deflection function series, i.e. in the present analysis two such equations are formed. A solution to these equations was found by utilising iterative techniques involving successive approximations. In the final analysis all parameters were non-dimensionalised to preserve generality.

As complete details of the aforementioned theoretical techniques are contained in (10) no further elaboration is deemed necessary. Rather, the present work will concentrate on the influence of initial imperfections on large planform orthotropic plates. In particular, the influence of unsymmetrical modes of initial deformation on the load carrying capabilities of such platework systems will be emphasised.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In the following discussions a plate aspect ratio $\lambda = 3.0$ will be chosen as an illustrative example. Although the present theoretical analysis can be reasonably applied to a spectrum of plate aspect ratios it is felt that $\lambda=3.0$ is sufficiently large to allow the singularities of large planform plates to be discussed.

Plates with Symmetrical Initial Deformations ($a_{011} \neq 0$, $a_{021} = 0$)

In order to illustrate the influence of symmetrical modes of initial plate deflections on the possibility of snap-buckling consider Figure 3. From this figure it is apparent that the nonlinearity of the load/deflection curve is greatly influenced by the magnitude of initial deflection coefficient, i.e. the degree of nonlinearity increases as a_{011} increases. However from a design point of view, it is reassuring to note that stable equilibrium conditions are predicted for $a_{011} \leq 5.0$. Above this value the possibility of snap-buckling becomes increasingly evident i.e. dynamic changes of shape are theoretically predicted. Also, permanent deformations in the inverted mode are indicated for $a_{011} \gg 10.0$. A number of other interesting points emerge from consideration of this figure e.g. the post-buckling stiffness would appear to be independent of the plate initial geometry. However, since the present investigation is primarily concerned with establishing design guidelines further discussion of the plate "post-buckling" characteristics will be omitted. By "post-buckling" is meant "that loading at which unacceptably large deflections are initiated".

At this stage it may be appropriate to reconsider the theoretical assumptions inherent in Figure 3. Perhaps the most relevant assumption is that the plate will remain symmetrically deformed throughout every stage of loading. At first glance this would appear to be a logical assumption since the plate is initially symmetrically deformed, symmetrically loaded and equally supported on all edges. However, if unsymmetric modes of deformation are theoretically allowed to occur at intermediate stages of loading, bifurcation of the equilibrium path is clearly predicted, Figure 4. It can be easily shown that this bifurcation phenomenon is theoretically limited to the limits shown in Figure 4.

So far as the plate is concerned it will clearly buckle at the minimum possible load i.e. the path of least resistance. Therefore combining the results of Figures 3 and 4 a summary of the possible buckling modes is obtained, Figure 5. This clearly shows that any design guidelines established assuming symmetrical modes of buckling would be considerably undermined by the presence of unsymmetrical or bifurcation buckling. For example in the case of a plate with an initial deflection ten times its thickness approximately 100% reduction in load carrying capacity is predicted.

Plates with Unsymmetrical Initial Deformations ($a_{011} \neq 0$, $a_{021} \neq 0$).

Figure 6 shows the load/deflection characteristics of a plate with an unsymmetrical mode of initial deflection. Shape can be considered to consist of two separate modes, one symmetrical and one asymmetrical, which superposition to give a resultant unsymmetrical shape. In order to illustrate the importance of any lack of symmetry on the plate initially deflected shape a typical example has been chosen i.e. the symmetrical coefficient a_{011} held constant at unity and the unsymmetrical coefficient a_{021} varied as shown. In this example the unsymmetrical component is seen to predominantly affect the large-deflection regime of the equilibrium path.

By reconsidering the results contained in Figure 5 to include the effects of unsymmetrical initial deflections and choosing an arbitrary value of symmetrical initial deflection Figure 7 is obtained. In this case the effect of increasing a_{021} is to negate the possibility of snap-buckling and induce a state of stable equilibrium throughout the load/deflection range i.e. no dynamic changes of shape are predicted.

In the case of a small aspect ration ($\lambda = 1.0$) the aforementioned effect is even more pronounced, Figure 8. For the square plate considered, increasing magnitudes of a_{021} are shown to dramatically alter the stability characteristics. Indeed, if sufficiently large magnitudes of a_{021} are present in the initially deflected shape ($a_{021} > 6.0$) stable equilibrium characteristics are predicted

through the range of useful loading. This is in accord with earlier published work (8) in plates with initial curvature.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A theoretical analysis of large-planform orthotropic rectangular plates with symmetrical initial deflections has been presented. The technique is sufficiently versatile to allow most practical modes of initial deformation to be analysed and corresponding stability characteristics determined. In particular, it has been clearly shown that unsymmetrical buckling greatly undermines previously established design criteria based on symmetrical considerations.

From a design viewpoint the present analysis has considerable advantages. Accepting that, in general, any initially deflected shape can be measured with relative ease using conventional measuring equipment. Thereafter the shape can be readily modelled using relatively few terms in the Fourier Series used to specify the initially deflected plate. The plate stability characteristics can then be computed. In a great many instances only two terms are necessary in the aforementioned series, one symmetrical and one asymmetrical, and results obtained using a programmable hand calculator without recourse to extensive computational facilities.

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NOTATION

- $a_{11}\omega_{11}/h$ non-dimensional plate central deflection
 $a_{011}\omega_{011}/h$ non-dimensional plate initial symmetrical deflection component
 $a_{021}\omega_{021}/h$ non-dimension-1 plate initial unsymmetrical deflection component
a, b plate length/breadth
 D_1 plate flexural rigidity in the major direction
 D_2 plate flexural rigidity in the minor direction
 D_3 plate twisting rigidity

E_x	Young's modulus of elasticity for x direction
E_y	Young's modulus of elasticity for y direction
F	Airy stress function
G_{xy}	modulus of rigidity
$\frac{h}{2}$	plate thickness
U	non-dimensional pressure loading - $\frac{q_z b^4}{E_y h^4}$
U_B	bending energy
U_P	load potential energy
U_S	mid-plane energy
U_T	total energy of the system
x, y	Cartesian coordinates
a	$\frac{E_y}{G} - 2\nu_y$
β	$\frac{E_y}{E_x}$ stiffness ratio
λ	plate aspect ratio = a/b
ν_x	Poisson's ratio with respect to the major direction
ω_{11}	symmetrical plate deflection coefficient
ω_{21}	unsymmetrical deflection coefficient.

FIG 1 TYPICAL LOAD/DEFLECTION RELATIONSHIP

FIG 2 CO-ORDINATE AXIS

FIG. 3 LOAD/DEFLECTION RELATIONSHIP

FIG. 4 LOAD/DEFLECTION RELATIONSHIP

FIG. 5 LOAD/DEFLECTION RELATIONSHIP

ERRATA

Proceedings of Fourth International Conference
on Composite Materials, Tokyo, Oct. 25-28, 1982,
pages 681-688, " Study on Elasto-plastic Fracture
Toughness of Composite Materials ", Megumu SUZUKI,
Masaharu IWAMOTO, Kazuyuki KIRIMURA, and Nobukazu
TANAKA

page 682, line 5, 5mm should be 10mm

page 682, line 5, 10mm should be 20mm

page 682, line 6, 4mm should be 8mm

page 682, line 7, 1mm should be 2mm

page 684, line 12, $K^2(1-\nu^2)$ should be $K^2(1-\nu^2)/E$

